

Synthesis of 6-Cinnamoylchromones

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Synthesis of 6-cinnamoyl-2,3-dimethylchromones (4), 6-cinnamoyl-3-methyl-2-phenylchromones (5) and 6-cinnamoyl-3-methylchromones (6) from 5-cinnamoyl-2-hydroxypropiophenone (3) has been described. The structures of the compounds have been brought out on the basis of their spectral data. The structures of 4 and 5 have also been corroborated by an alternate synthesis involving condensation of 2,3-dimethyl-6-acetylchromones (7) and 3-methyl-2-phenyl-6-acetylchromones (8) with aromatic aldehydes respectively.

α,β -Unsaturated ketones are versatile intermediates in the synthesis of a wide variety of heterocyclic systems¹. In continuation of our work on the synthesis of flavonoids and substituted chromones of potential medicinal interest and with a view to evolve a convenient route for the synthesis of chromones having different heterocyclic rings, it was considered worthwhile to synthesise some 6-cinnamoylchromones (4–6). In the present paper we report a convenient three-step synthesis of the title compounds commencing with commercially available *o*-hydroxypropiophenone (1). As depicted in Scheme 1, the procedure of Da Re *et al.*² for Friedel-Crafts acetylation of 1, has been modified to afford high yield of 5-acetyl-2-hydroxypropiophenone (2).

Claisen condensation of 2 with appropriate aromatic aldehydes in the presence of methanolic potassium hydroxide yielded 5-cinnamoyl-2-hydroxypropiophenones (3) in 85–90% yield. An interesting feature of the reaction is that it is selective, propionyl group remaining unaffected even when a large excess of aromatic aldehyde was used.

Condensation of 3 with acetic anhydride in presence of fused sodium acetate or benzoyl chloride in presence of sodium benzoate according to Kostanecki-Robinson procedure³, afforded 6-cinnamoyl-2,3-dimethylchromones (4) and 6-cinnamoyl-3-methyl-2-phenylchromones (5) respectively, in 80–85% yields. The structures of these compounds were in conformity with their elemental analyses and spectral data. The structures of 4 and 5 were also confirmed by an alternate unambiguous synthesis of these compounds by the condensation of 6-acetyl-2,3-dimethylchromones (7) and 6-acetyl-3-methyl-2-phenylchromones (8), respectively, with appropriate aromatic aldehydes in dry benzene in presence of piperidine.

6-Cinnamoyl-3-methylchromones (6) were synthesised by the treatment of 3 with dimethylformamide (DMF) and $\text{BF}_3 \cdot \text{Et}_2\text{O}$ in presence of methanesulphonyl chloride⁴. The structural assignments of these compounds were based on elemental analyses and spectral data.

The present route for the synthesis of 4–6 involving improvement in the intermediate step (1→2) is quite convenient giving high yields of these compounds.

Scheme 1. Reagents: (i) CH_3COCl and 1 added to AlCl_3 suspension in CS_2 (reverse addition), (ii) ArCHO , $\text{KOH} \cdot \text{MeOH}$ at room temperature, (iii) $(\text{CH}_3\text{CO})_2\text{O}$ and CH_3COONa at $170-80^\circ$, (iv) $\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{COCl}$ and $\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{COONa}$ at $170-80^\circ$. (v) $\text{CH}_3\text{SO}_2\text{Cl}$, $\text{BF}_3 \cdot \text{Et}_2\text{O}$ and DMF and (vi) ArCHO , piperidine in benzene.

Experimental

All melting points were taken in open capillaries in sulphuric acid bath and are uncorrected. Ir spectra (nujol) were recorded on a Beckman IR-20 spectrophotometer, pmr spectra (CDCl_3) on a Perkin-Elmer R-32 (90 MHz) instrument using TMS as an internal standard and mass spectra on a Hewlett-Packard GC/MS 5985 instrument (70 eV).

5-Acetyl-2-hydroxypropiophenone (2) : It was prepared in 90% yield by the modification of the reported method², and the modification involved addition of a mixture of 1 and acetyl chloride to the suspension of AlCl₃ in CS₂ (reverse addition).

5-Cinnamoyl-2-hydroxypropiophenones (3). *General procedure* : To a solution of KOH (0.02 mol) in methanol (15 ml) was added 2 (0.01 mol) followed by appropriate aromatic aldehyde (0.01 mol) and the mixture was stirred for 24 h at room temperature. The resulting deep reddish solution was poured in ice-cold dilute HCl (10%). The solid obtained was washed with water and crystallised from ethanol to give 3 (Table 1) : ν_{\max} 3 400–3 200 (OH), 1 660 (C=O α , β -unsaturated ketones) and 1 640 cm⁻¹ (C=O H-bonded); 3a δ 1.28 (3H, t, *J* 7.0 Hz, benzene C₁-COCH₂CH₃), 3.18 (2H, q, *J* 7.0 Hz, benzene C₂-COCH₂CH₃), 7.08 (1H, d, *J* 9.0 Hz, benzene C₃-H), 7.40–7.56 (3H, m, aryl C₅-H, C₄'-H and C₆'-H), 7.60–7.76 (3H, m, aryl C₂-H, C₆-H and olefinic H_B), 7.87 (1H, d, *J* 16.0 Hz, olefinic H_A), 8.16 (1H, dd *J* 9.0 Hz and 2.5 Hz, benzene C₄-H), 8.56 (1H, d, *J* 2.5 Hz, benzene C₆-H) and 12.80 (1H, s, exchangeable with D₂O, benzene, C₂-OH).

6-Cinnamoyl-2,3-dimethylchromones (4). *General procedure* : A mixture of 3 (0.01 mol), fused sodium acetate (2.4 g) and acetic anhydride (5 ml) was heated on an oil-bath at 170–80° for 8 h. The fused mass was cooled to room temperature and taken up in water. The resulting solid was washed with water, dried and crystallised from alcohol to afford 4 (Table 1).

6-Cinnamoyl-3-methyl-2-phenylchromone (5). *General procedure* : A mixture of 3 (0.01 mol), benzoyl chloride (3 ml) and anhydrous sodium benzoate (6 g) was heated in an oil-bath at 170–80° for 7–8 h. The reaction mixture was then poured in water, filtered, washed with water and extracted with chloroform. The chloroform extract was washed with aqueous sodium bicarbonate solution followed by water, dried and distilled to remove the solvent. The residual solid was crystallised from ethanol to yield 5 (Table 1).

6-Cinnamoyl-2,3-dimethylchromones (4 and 5). *Alternate method. General procedure* : To a mixture of 6-acetyl-2,3-dimethylchromone (7; 0.01 mol) or 6-acetyl-3-methyl-2-phenylchromone (8; 0.01 mol) and appropriate aromatic aldehyde (0.011 mol) in dry benzene (200 ml) was added piperidine (3–4 drops) and the mixture was refluxed on an oil-bath for 18 h using Dean-Stark apparatus to remove water. The solvent was then removed under reduced pressure and the resulting gummy mass was taken up in ethyl acetate (150 ml). The solution was washed with 10% HCl (2 × 100 ml) followed by water (3 × 100 ml). The organic layer was then dried (Na₂SO₄) and the mixture was purified by passing through a column of silica gel G (60–120 mesh) using ethyl acetate-petroleum ether (1 : 9) as eluant to afford 4 (Table 1).

TABLE I—PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS 3–6*

Compd. no.	Ar	Yield† %	M.p.** °C	Mol. formula (M ⁺ , m/z)
3a	C ₆ H ₅	90	120–21	C ₁₈ H ₁₆ O ₃
b	4-Cl-C ₆ H ₄	90	121–22	C ₁₈ H ₁₅ ClO ₃
c	4-CH ₃ -C ₆ H ₄	90	142–43	C ₁₉ H ₁₈ O ₃
d	4-CH ₃ O-C ₆ H ₄	88	129–30	C ₁₉ H ₁₈ O ₄
e	3,4-(CH ₃ O) ₂ -C ₆ H ₃	85	125–26	C ₂₀ H ₂₀ O ₅
4a	C ₆ H ₅	80 (66)	171–72	C ₂₀ H ₁₈ O ₃ (304)
b	4-Cl-C ₆ H ₄	80 (70)	209–11	C ₂₀ H ₁₇ ClO ₃ (338/340)
c	4-CH ₃ -C ₆ H ₄	85 (70)	192–93	C ₂₁ H ₁₈ O ₃
d	4-CH ₃ O-C ₆ H ₄	82	200–02	C ₂₁ H ₁₈ O ₄ (334)
e	3,4-(CH ₃ O) ₂ -C ₆ H ₃	84	145–46	C ₂₂ H ₂₀ O ₅
5a	C ₆ H ₅	80 (65)	179–80	C ₂₀ H ₁₈ O ₃
b	4'-Cl-C ₆ H ₄	85 (65)	220	C ₂₅ H ₁₇ ClO ₃
c	4'-CH ₃ -C ₆ H ₄	80 (70)	202–03	C ₂₄ H ₂₀ O ₃
d	4'-CH ₃ O-C ₆ H ₄	85	178–80	C ₂₆ H ₂₀ O ₄
e	3,4-(CH ₃ O) ₂ -C ₆ H ₃	82	114–15	C ₂₇ H ₂₂ O ₅
6a	C ₆ H ₅	74	154–56	C ₁₉ H ₁₄ O ₃
b	4-Cl-C ₆ H ₄	78	187–89	C ₁₉ H ₁₃ ClO ₃
c	4-CH ₃ -C ₆ H ₄	82	169–70	C ₂₀ H ₁₆ O ₃
d	4-CH ₃ O-C ₆ H ₄	76	149–50	C ₂₀ H ₁₆ O ₄

* Satisfactory C and H analysis were obtained for all the compounds. ** All compounds were crystallised from ethanol, except 6a–d (benzene-petroleum ether).

† Yield obtained by alternate methods in parenthesis.

‡ a(M) : (M+2) = 3 : 1.

In addition to being transparent at 3 400–3 200 (OH of 3), 4 and 5 exhibited ir bands at 1 660 (C=O of 6-cinnamoyl moiety) and 1 635–1 630 cm⁻¹ (C=O of the chromone system); 4a δ 2.06 (3H, s, chromone C₃-CH₃), 2.40 (3H, s, chromone C₅-CH₃), 7.35–7.50 (4H, m, aryl C₅-H, C₄'-H, C₆'-H and chromone C₃-H), 7.53–7.72 (3H, m, aryl C₂-H, C₆'-H and olefinic H_B), 7.88 (1H, d, *J* 16.0 Hz, olefinic H_A), 8.30 (1H, dd, *J* 2.5 Hz and 9.0 Hz, chromone C₇-H) and 8.81 (1H, d, *J* 2.5 Hz, chromone C₈-H); 5a δ 2.22 (3H, s, chromone C₃-CH₃), 7.50–7.82 (12H, complex m, 10 × ArH, chromone C₈-H and olefinic H_B), 7.95 (1H, d, *J* 16.0 Hz, olefinic H_A), 8.40 (1H, dd, *J* 2.5 Hz and 9.0 Hz, chromone C₇-H) and 8.91 (1H, d, *J* 2.5 Hz, chromone C₈-H).

6-Cinnamoyl-3-methylchromones (6). *General procedure* : A solution of 3 (0.01 mol) in dimethylformamide (20 ml) was treated cautiously with BF₃·Et₂O (0.04 mol) when a vigorous exothermic reaction occurred. To this mixture was added dropwise with constant stirring, a solution of methanesulphonyl chloride (0.03 mol) in dimethylformamide (5 ml) at 50°. The mixture was then heated on the water-bath for 2 h. It was cooled to room temperature and poured into the ice-cold water with rapid stirring. The resulting solid was washed with water, dried and crystallised from benzene-petroleum ether to afford 6 (Table 1).

As in case of 4, these compounds were also transparent at 3 400–3 200 (OH of 3). They, however,

exhibited ir bands at 1 655 (C=O of 6-cinnamoyl moiety) and 1 635 cm^{-1} (C=O of chromone ring); δ 2.08 (3H, s, chromone C₃-CH₃), 7.35–8.02 (9H, m, chromone C₂-H and C₈-H, olefinic H_A and H_B and aryl C₂'-H, C₃'-H, C₄'-H, C₅'-H and C₆'-H), 8.45 (1H, dd, *J* 2.5 Hz and 9.0 Hz, chromone C₇-H) and 8.88 (1H, d, *J* 2.5 Hz, chromone C₅-H).

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